

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TRENDS IN EMERGING RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TRENDS IN EMERGING RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

Volume 2; Issue 2; 2024; Page No. 43-46

Received: 14-12-2023

Accepted: 27-02-2024

Impact of yoga and classical dance on academic achievement

¹Vijayta Jain and ²Dr. Samar Jeet Singh

¹Research Scholar, Sam Global University, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India

²Professor, Sam Global University, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12737333>

Corresponding Author: Vijayta Jain

Abstract

Traditional dance and yoga are two of the world's oldest forms of self-improvement that focus on the whole person. The ultimate goal of both yoga and classical dance is the development of a healthy mind, body, and soul. Students in the ninth grade from the Visakhapatnam District in Andhra Pradesh will be the focus of this research on the effects of yoga and classical dance on their academic performance. Students' academic performance is being impacted by his academic stress. Students are unable to satisfy the demands of today's educational system since their memory have become dull and foggy as a result of academic stress. Students' improved physical health as a result of yoga and dance classes may have a positive impact on their academic performance, according to the study.

Keywords: Yoga, Indian classical dance, Spirituality and Academic Achievement

Introduction

The phrase "Indian classical dance" (also known as "Shastri Nriya") encompasses a variety of dance styles that have their origins in Hindu musical theatre performances and whose principles and practices may be traced back to the Sanskrit book Natya Shastra. According to various sources and scholars, there are six to twelve different classical dance styles in India. The Sangeet Natak Academy, which is dedicated to preserving Indian arts, recognises eight of these styles: Bharatanatyam, Kathak, Kuchipudi, Odissi, Kathakali, Sattriya, Manipuri, and Mohiniyattam.

In addition, Chhau is one of nine styles recognised by the Indian Ministry of Culture. Academics like Drid Williams expand the list to include Chhau, Yakshagana, and Bhagavata Mela. distinct regions and states in India are the birthplace of distinct dance traditions; for instance, the southern Indian state of Tamil Nadu is the birthplace of Bharatanatyam, the eastern Indian state of Odisha is the birthplace of Odissi, and the northeastern Indian state of Manipur is the birthplace of Manipuri. A wide variety of dance forms, costumes, and expressions are shown in these performances, set to music in a wide variety of Indian-Subcontinental languages such as Hindi, Malayalam,

Sanskrit, Tamil, Odia, Telugu, and many more.

Traditional and modern yoga is practiced worldwide, and there are many different schools of yoga within Hinduism, Buddhism, and Jainism. Yoga is a set of physical, mental, and spiritual disciplines that originated in ancient India. Its goal is to control and still the mind, to recognise an unattached witness-consciousness that is unaffected by the mind (Chitta), and to alleviate mundane suffering (Duḥkha). The Rigveda, an ancient Hindu book, is the first place where yoga-like activities are addressed. There are several references to yoga throughout the Upanishads. The word "yoga" with its current definition first appears in the Katha Upanishad, a text likely written in the fifth or third century BCE. In the ascetic and Śramaṇa traditions of ancient India, yoga persisted as a disciplined study and practice in the fifth and sixth century BCE. In the early years of the Common Era, Patanjali wrote the Yoga Sutras, the most extensive literature on yoga. By the middle of the first century CE, Yoga philosophy had established itself as one of Hinduism's six traditional philosophical traditions, or Darśanas. From tantra, Hatha yoga books emerged in the ninth and eleventh centuries.

Literature Review

Basu, Arnab. (2024) ^[1]. A growing body of evidence points to the many physical, mental, and spiritual benefits of yoga, an ancient Indian practice that has recently received widespread attention throughout the world. Originating in the ancient Indian scriptures of the Bhagavad Gita, the Yoga Sutras, the Upanishads, and the Vedas, yoga provides a holistic method for personal development. With a focus on how it may be used to integrate spirituality into everyday life, this research study examines the relevance of yoga as described in these ancient texts. Through an analysis of the texts' philosophical underpinnings, practical procedures, and spiritual insights, this research elucidates how yoga may be a tool for personal and collective spiritual development and awakening.

Zafeiroudi, Aglaia. (2021) ^[2]. Awakening to one's spirituality may be facilitated by rhythmic response, physical activity, and similar practices. A common thread running through both dance and yoga is an emphasis on the body-mind connection. As forms of spiritual physical practice, this article reviews the literature on yoga and modern/contemporary dance. The incorporation of modern and contemporary dance into yoga practice was the subject of an electronic literature search that used Scopus, Google Scholar, CINAHL, EMBASE, PubMed/MEDLINE, and Web of Science databases. Coordinating bodily motions with breath, rhythm, gestures, and energy management are only a few of the many significant choreographic and spiritual parallels highlighted by the study. Graham is only one of several modern and contemporary artists, choreographers, and dancers that incorporate yoga into their work. The physical motions of yoga and dance help one become more self-aware and self-perceived, which in turn helps one establish a connection between their physical, mental, and spiritual selves and the divine. At last, the article explains and proposes a way to use rhythm and music with these two practices to improve spirituality via movement. This study aimed to broaden the ways in which spirituality and movement, namely yoga and modern/contemporary dance, might be thought about and done.

Gupta, Jyoti. (2024) ^[3]. Your Daily Yoga Practice and Its Significance. The ancient Indian practice of yoga has recently grown in popularity across the world due to its many well-rounded advantages, such as improved health, sharper focus, less stress, and better relationships. Yoga has several benefits, including helping with stress, sleep, and weight management. This article discusses the eight stages of yoga's growth and how they may be accessed by varied demographics. Scientific studies have shown that yoga improves the quality of life for people with RA. The Czech Association for Yoga in Everyday Life promotes health, compassion, environmental protection, and cultural tolerance via its yoga programmes. For its millions of devotees throughout the globe, yoga is a panacea for health; it improves their emotional, mental, social, and spiritual lives simultaneously.

Gronek, Piotr & Gronek, Joanna & Karpińska, Aleksandra & Woźniewicz-Dobrzyńska, Małgorzata & Wycichowska, Paulina. (2021) ^[4]. Everything Kinesthetic-movements, gestures, stances, leaps, turns, shifting body weight, etc.-is inextricably linked with dancing. In this way, dancing may be seen as both an amateur's display of talent and a highly trained athlete's performance. Emotions are an integral part of dance, both as an expression and a narrative device in choreography. Additionally, dance is structured to generate a wide variety of styles and approaches. Improvisation in this style is unlike any other. The dancing body, however, may bring the dancer closer to his or her emotions and even spirituality in certain contexts, styles, and approaches that will be covered later on. Consequently, this philosophical investigation seeks to examine the effect of religion on dance performances.

Chatterjee, A. (1992) ^[5]. Indian classical, folk, and contemporary dance styles and their therapeutic benefits. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies in the Humanities (Rupkatha)*, volume 5, pages 75–83. Dancing offers a great opportunity for physical, mental, and emotional wellness since it is an energetic, non-competitive kind of exercise. The premise that the mind and body are interdependent is the basis of dance therapy. A relatively recent development in the field of dance writing is the therapeutic use of Indian dances in its many forms. As a kind of treatment and self-awareness, dancing was revered in Ayurveda (psychology). Music, dance, and song (Sangeet) have been shown to have positive effects on people's physical and mental health, and this is backed up by Indian philosophy as well. Bhangra (Punjab), Karagam (Tamil Nadu), Chou, Rayabese, and Dhali (West Bengal) are all strong dance forms that promote health and strength. Anger and stress may be released via the rapid footwork of Kathak dancing. To dance the Manipuri style, one must use smooth, rounded motions free of abrupt stops, angles, or straight lines. It brings them tranquilly, good body control, and a gentle, undulating look. Therapeutic movements are greatly impacted by all of these body motions, balance, expressiveness, muscular action, muscle constriction, and relaxation. Dance therapists in modern India are aware of this, and they adapt their improvisational dance moves to meet the needs of their clients.

Materials and Methods

Examining how Yoga and classical dance affect the academic performance of ninth graders in the Visakhapatnam District of Andhra Pradesh is the purpose of the current research. Both boys and girls made up the 160-person student body. This was determined by administering pre- and post-training tests to each group and comparing the resulting gains to either support or refute the investigator's theory. In order to ensure that the two groups were as similar as feasible, we compared their accomplishment results on the quarterly test. The experimental group was given instruction in classical dance and yoga. The current research employed the test-retest procedure to assess the

reliability of the instruments. A total of fifty pupils were first administered all of the examinations. Colour and word stooing An attention-and concentration-test, an academic stress scale, a memory test using the Ebbinghaus nonsense syllables list, and end-of-semester and midterm grades were all used to assess the students' academic progress. A pre-test was carried out at the outset of the experiment utilising the several instruments used for the task. The investigator used SPSS Package version 13.0 to analyse the experimental data. Means, standard deviations, and t-scores were computed for each group.

Data Analysis

In order to find hidden facts, the investigator reviewed the organised material. The data was examined from several perspectives in order to uncover fresh information. The collection, organisation, analysis, and numerical data processing have all benefited substantially from the statistical methods.

Following completion of data collection, it was analysed with the study's aims and hypotheses in mind. There are four main components to this research. Finding out how Yoga and Dance affected Concentration and Memory, Academic Stress, and Academic Performance was the primary goal of the research. The results of the Academic, Memory, SASS, and Stoop tests. The data for the research came from achievement exams. Statistical analysis was performed on these scores. We used statistical tests to confirm or disprove each of our theories. Consequently, the data was subjected to statistical analysis, the outcomes of which are detailed on the following pages.

Table 1: Comparison between the pre-test scores of the experimental and control groups on stroop test.

		Experimental Group (n=80)	Control Group (n=80)	T
Dots Time	Mean	36.742	35.943	0.6317
	S.D	8.853	7.043	
Dots errors	Mean	3.690	3.782	0.2048
	S.D	2.932	2.745	
Words time	Mean	47.752	47.0420	0.6251
	S.D	8.312	5.842	
Words errors	Mean	2.742	2.939	0.3319
	S.D	3.953	3.542	
Colours time	Mean	51.477	52.363	0.6269
	S.D	8.932	8.945	
Colours errors	Mean	9.0441	10.797	1.5152
	S.D	4.761	9.187	
Total time	Mean	135.971	135.348	0.1367
	S.D	26.094	21.83	
Total errors	Mean	15.4761	17.518	0.9430
	S.D	11.646	15.474	

* Significant at 0.05 level **Significant at 0.01 level

The acquired t-scores with respect to different components of the stroop test are not significant at the 0.05 level, as can be seen from table-1. This finding suggests that the experimental group and the control group did not differ in

their performance across the many aspects of the stroop test. Additionally, it was determined that the experimental group and the control group in this research were pre-matched.

Table 2: Performance of the experimental group on stroop-test (n=80).

		Pre-Test	Post-Test	t
Dots Time	Mean	22.542	20.32	1.88775
	S.D	8.42	6.32	
Dots errors	Mean	2.634	1.473	3.5395**
	S.D	2.432	1.641	
Words time	Mean	29.658	25.321	4.3797**
	S.D	6.742	5.744	
Words errors	Mean	9.551	7.631	4.1328**
	S.D	3.370	2.431	
Colours time	Mean	29.348	25.313	2.2953*
	S.D	11.483	10.741	
Colours errors	Mean	9.482	5.632	6.0278**
	S.D	4.7432	3.184	
Total time	Mean	81.548	70.954	2.70176**
	S.D	26.645	22.805	
Total errors	Mean	21.667	14.736	4.84302**
	S.D	10.5452	7.256	

* Significant at 0.05 level **Significant at 0.01 level

Table 2 clearly shows that the experimental group's stroop test performance decreased dramatically across the board, including all components such as dot time, dot mistakes, words time, colours time, colours errors, total time, and total errors. There is a statistically significant change in the t-scores obtained from the stroop test's different components; this difference might be attributable to the therapy with yoga and dancing.

Table 3: Performance of the control group on stroop test (n=80)

		Pre-Test	Post-test	t
Dots Time	Mean	24.32	22.501	1.6665
	S.D	7.939	5.6816	
Dots errors	Mean	2.394	2.549	0.3325
	S.D	2.843	3.049	
Words time	Mean	26.418	25.363	0.6629
	S.D	8.481	11.432	
Words errors	Mean	7.933	9.432	1.0841
	S.D	8.542	8.943	
Colours time	Mean	36.743	35.393	1.05572
	S.D	8.321	7.823	
Colours errors	Mean	13.843	11.843	1.5906
	S.D	8.743	7.073	
Total time	Mean	87.481	83.257	1.0755
	S.D	24.741	24.9366	
Total errors	Mean	24.17	23.824	0.11162
	S.D	20.128	19.065	

Table 3 shows that the control group's t-scores on the stroop test did not change significantly between the pre- and post-tests. This is in accordance with the results of the other stroop test components. The control group may have lacked the yoga and dance therapy, which might explain this.

Table 4: Comparison between the post test scores of the experimental and control groups on stroop test

		Control Group (n=80)	Experimental Group (n=80)	t
Dots Time	Mean	35.321	30.934	3.5546**
	S.D	8.243	7.342	
Dots errors	Mean	7.799	6.432	4.2812**
	S.D	1.432	2.471	
Words time	Mean	35.071	30.32	4.4455**
	S.D	5.742	7.642	
Words errors	Mean	9.213	4.43	7.2186**
	S.D	4.032	4.34	
Colours time	Mean	38.391	20.621	5.1129**
	S.D	8.742	29.831	
Colours errors	Mean	38.642	3.743	7.1241**
	S.D	33.432	28.321	
Total time	Mean	108.783	81.875	4.7896**
	S.D	22.727	44.815	
Total errors	Mean	55.65	14.6	7.11**
	S.D	38.896	35.132	

* Significant at 0.05 level ** Significant at 0.01 level

Table 4 shows that the t-scores for the post-test scores on the different stroop test components vary significantly between the control and experimental groups. A statistically significant reduction was seen across the board in the experimental group on the stroop test. This could be because the experimental group had an intervention that included yoga and dancing.

Table 5: Comparison between the pre-test score of experimental and control groups on SASS

		Experimental group (n=80)	Control Group (n=80)	t
Personal inadequacy	Mean	29.774	30.843	0.6262
	S.D	12.832	8.271	
Fear of failure	Mean	24.822	28.682	1.76507
	S.D	14.631	12.982	
Interpersonal difficulties	Mean	28.842	29.251	0.3263
	S.D	8.732	7.031	
Teacher pupil relationships	Mean	29.79	31.063	0.9437
	S.D	8.836	8.214	
Inadequate facilities	Mean	30.26	30.842	0.45405
	S.D	8.891	7.238	
Total	Mean	143.488	150.681	0.9266
	S.D	53922	43.736	

* Significant at 0.05 level **Significant at 0.01 level

Conclusions

The primary goal of this research was to find out how Yoga and Classical Dance affected students' performance in the classroom. Academic stress, memory, and concentration were shown to be the most significant elements affecting academic achievement. The overarching goal of the research was to determine whether or not classical dance and yoga had any effect on students' ability to concentrate, memory, and overall academic performance. A total of 160 ninth graders from four different schools in Visakhapatnam and the surrounding area were randomly selected to participate in the study. "Complete Experimental Simple requirement group pre-test and post-test Experimental design" was the step-by-step guide that the research took. Most of the conclusions were reached by comparing the Experimental and Control groups' pre- and post-test results.

References

- Basu A. The Ancient Indian Texts and the Importance of Yoga in Incorporating Spiritualism. *Am J Bus Manag Res.* 2024;5:38-55. doi:10.15864/ajbmr.5104.
- Zafeioudi A. Intersections between Modern and Contemporary Dance and Yoga Practice: A Critical Analysis of Spiritual Paths through Body Movement and Choreography. *Acad J Interdiscip Stud.* 2021;10(1):doi:10.36941/ajis-2021-0094.
- Gupta J. Importance of Yoga in Everyday Life; c2024. p. 72-77.
- Gronek P, Gronek J, Karpińska A, Woźniewicz-Dobrzyńska M, Wycichowska P. Is Dance Closer to Physical Activity or Spirituality? A Philosophical Exploration. *J Relig Health.* 2021;62. doi:10.1007/s10943-021-01354-y.
- Chatterjee A. The therapeutic value of Indian classical, folk and innovative dance Joshi LN, Joshi VD, Gokhale LV. Effect of short-term pranayama practice on the breathing rate and the ventilatory functions of the lung. *Indian J Physiol Pharmacol.* 1992;36:105-108.
- Khumar SS, Kaur P, Kaur S. Effectiveness of shavasana on depression among university students. *Indian J Clin Psychol forms.* Rupkatha J Interdiscip Stud Humanit. 1993;20:82-87.
- Kamraju M, Prathaap S. How to avoid rejection of research paper by journals. *Int J Res Anal Rev.* 2019;6:732-738.
- Ali MA, Kamraju M. Influence of physical Education and sports in students' life. *Int Fed Comput Sci Sports;* c2017. p. 78-79.
- Ali MA, Kamraju M. Importance of health and Fitness in life. *Int Fed Comp Sci Sports;* c2017. p. 41-43.
- Yoga N. OED Online. Oxford: Oxford University Press. Available from: <https://www.en.wikipedia.org/wiki/yoga>. [Last accessed on 2015 Sep 09].
- Golden SAR. Rural students' attitude towards English as medium of instruction in higher education—an analysis. *Int J Res.* 2016;3:1-10.
- Telles S, Reddy SK, Nagendra HR. Oxygen consumption and respiration following two yoga relaxation techniques. *Appl Psychophysiol Biofeedback.* 2000;25:221–227.
- Singh RH, Udupa KN. Psychobiological studies on certain hatha yoga practices. Paper presented at: International Seminar on Stress in Health and Diseases; Varanasi: Banaras Hindu University; c1977.
- Datey KK. Stress and heart diseases and how to control it with newer techniques—biofeedback and Savanasana. Paper presented at: International Seminar on Stress in Health and Diseases; Varanasi: Banaras Hindu University; c1977.

Creative Commons (CC) License

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) license. This license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.